

EMAC TranPul Simulation Data

Given here is the data of the tranPul simulation, as described and used in the ACP(D) publication <https://www.atmos-chem-phys-discuss.net/acp-2019-974/> and the resulting final publication. The simulation was obtained using ECHAM/MESSy. Details on the setup and version are given in the metadata of the netcdf file which is uploaded here and in the ACP(D) article. The data is given as monthly mean, zonal mean fields on pressure levels. Included in the dataset are the inert tracer pulses, that are used to obtain age of air spectra, and the linear AoA tracer.